

CONDITIONS FOR IMPLEMENTING INTELLIGENT DECISION SUPPORT IN THE PREVENTIVE MAINTENANCE SYSTEM OF EQUIPMENT AT AN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISE

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Abstract. The article highlights the relevance of implementing intelligent decision support in the preventive maintenance system of industrial equipment. The possibilities of using artificial intelligence methods, machine learning, and expert systems to enhance equipment reliability, prevent failures, and minimize unplanned downtime are examined. The key factors influencing the successful implementation of intelligent technologies are characterized, including maturity level, data availability, and the enterprise's readiness for digital transformation. The necessity of a preliminary assessment of the enterprise's maturity level and its preventive maintenance system is emphasized. The task of determining ways to create and ensure the necessary conditions for the implementation of intelligent decision support is set. The stages of knowledge base formation, data structuring, decision support algorithm development, and their integration with corporate management systems are considered. The provision of conditions for implementation is examined, including data standardization, failure analysis, and predictive fault forecasting. A description of the implementation stages is provided, along with steps and actions ensuring the effective use of intelligent technologies. The characteristics of potential risks are outlined, including data limitations, technical barriers, personnel resistance, and financial constraints. The results of the analysis of existing approaches are presented, and the development paths of intelligent systems in preventive maintenance, as well as risk mitigation mechanisms during their deployment, are discussed. In conclusion, it is stated that the successful implementation of intelligent decision support requires a systematic approach, adherence to the implementation sequence, and adaptation to the enterprise's maturity level. The proposed approach provides the necessary conditions for a gradual transition to intelligent management, improving maintenance efficiency, reducing operational risks, and laying the foundation for further digitalization of the industrial enterprise. **Keywords:** Intelligent decision support; Maintenance and repair; Digital transformation; Machine learning; Predictive analytics; Digitalization, system.

INTRODUCTION

Ensuring uninterrupted production processes and the safe operation of technological equipment at a chemical industry enterprise is one of the key tasks. Preventive maintenance,

as a strategic tool within the maintenance and repair (M&R) system, plays a crucial role in maintaining equipment reliability and preventing emergency downtime [1]. However, traditional methods of managing preventive maintenance within the enterprise's M&R system face increasing challenges associated with technological advancements, growing data volumes, and the need for rapid decision-making [2].

In this regard, the implementation of intelligent decision support systems (IDSS) becomes an important direction for modernizing the M&R system. Studies indicate that the application of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) methods helps reduce incident response times and optimize resource utilization [3]. Feedback sensors, Internet of Things (IoT) technologies, and predictive analytics are seen as tools for automating and improving equipment maintenance processes [4]. Intelligent management methods for technical systems contribute to enhancing the reliability and safety of complex systems [5].

However, successful implementation of IDSS in M&R management requires meeting certain conditions, one of which is achieving a certain level of process maturity within the enterprise [6]. In this context, the maturity level is defined by the degree of integration of modern maintenance and repair practices with the company's operational processes, as well as its readiness to adopt intelligent solutions. Assessing maturity levels enables the identification of strengths and weaknesses in the M&R system, determination of necessary improvements, and development of a strategy for gradually implementing intelligent decision support methods [7].

The relevance of this study is driven by the need to define the conditions under which a high-quality transition to intelligent decision-making processes within the M&R system of an industrial enterprise becomes feasible. In practice, the maturity level of production companies in organizing M&R processes varies significantly, necessitating a differentiated approach to implementing IDSS. The lack of a systematic approach to evaluating initial conditions and influencing factors in IDSS implementation introduces risks of planning errors, potentially leading to inefficient resource use and reduced expected benefits from intelligent technologies. Therefore, the task of making well-grounded choices of intelligent support methods and developing algorithms that can adapt to different maturity levels and account for the specifics of the enterprise's production and organizational environment becomes particularly relevant.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

Implementing an IDSS requires a comprehensive analysis of the current state of the M&R system. As a methodological foundation for such analysis, it is advisable to use maturity level assessment methods [8], which allow for an objective determination of an enterprise's readiness to adopt intelligent technologies and transition to intelligent M&R management processes. The stages of assessing M&R system maturity levels, reflecting the logic of analysis and conclusion formation about readiness for IDSS implementation, are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Stages of assessing enterprise maturity level.

Stage	Actions
Analysis of the current M&R system state	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Study of existing maintenance and repair processes. - Evaluation of data availability and quality on equipment. - Identification of methods used for failure analysis and prediction.
Identification of key maturity factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Availability of digital equipment data. - Use of standardized M&R regulations. - Application of analytical methods in repair management.
Enterprise classification by maturity levels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Initial</i> (reactive maintenance, lack of data). - <i>Basic</i> (preliminary planning based on standards). - <i>Advanced</i> (predictive methods, failure analytics). - <i>Optimized</i> (full digitalization of M&R, intelligent systems).
Determination of conditions for transitioning to the next maturity level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of strategies for data collection, processing, and analysis. - Implementation of mechanisms for building a knowledge base.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gradual integration of intelligent algorithms.

Fig. 1 presents the key results that define the opportunities and directions for IDSS implementation.

Fig. 1. Key results of the M&R system maturity assessment stage.

Let us examine these key results in more detail:

- A comprehensive view of the current state of the enterprise’s M&R system. Analyzing existing processes, data quality and availability, and the applied management methods provides a holistic view of the current organization level of M&R processes. This includes:
 - o Determining the extent to which maintenance procedures are regulated;
 - o Identifying weaknesses in the collection and processing of equipment data;
 - o Assessing the maturity of the analytical and predictive methods used. This result forms the foundation for management decisions regarding necessary changes and priority development areas within the M&R system.
- Classification of the enterprise by M&R maturity level. Based on the identified maturity factors, the enterprise is given a clear position on the maturity scale, which includes:
 - o *Initial* (dominance of reactive maintenance),
 - o *Basic* (use of regulatory documents and plans),
 - o *Advanced* (application of predictive analytics and forecasting models),

- *Optimized* (complete digitalization and implementation of intelligent management algorithms). This classification allows for an objective evaluation of the enterprise's readiness to implement IDSS and to align it with modern requirements and best industry practices.
- Development of well-founded recommendations and a strategy for transitioning to the next maturity level. The analysis results in a list of necessary conditions for moving to a higher maturity level, which includes:
 - Strategies for improving the quality and completeness of technical equipment data;
 - Plans for implementing digital tools and analytical methods;
 - Measures for creating and populating a knowledge base to support intelligent algorithms;
 - Justification of the stages for integrating IDSS into the existing M&R system. This enables the formation of a specific “roadmap” for the step-by-step implementation of IDSS, taking into account the enterprise's resource capabilities and organizational readiness.
- Minimizing the risks of ineffective implementation of intelligent systems. An objective assessment of an enterprise's maturity and readiness allows for the avoidance of common implementation mistakes, such as:
 - Excessive investment in technologies that the enterprise is not fully prepared to utilize;
 - Choosing intelligent support methods that do not align with the actual capabilities of the enterprise;
 - Organizational and methodological errors in the planning of changes.

As a result, the enterprise increases the efficiency of resource usage, minimizes risks, and establishes real prerequisites for the successful digital transformation of its M&R system.

Thus, assessing the maturity level of the M&R system is a necessary preliminary step on the path to implementing intelligent decision support systems in an industrial enterprise. The results obtained make it possible not only to objectively assess the current capabilities of the enterprise but also to form a realistic development strategy for the M&R system, taking into account specific conditions and limitations.

The implementation of IDSS for preventive maintenance tasks is impossible without a clear understanding of the available methods and algorithms for data processing, equipment condition analysis, and generating well-founded recommendations for M&R management. The choice of specific intelligent support methods directly depends on the maturity level of the enterprise and the readiness of its M&R system to utilize digital and analytical tools.

For each maturity level, it is advisable to define a specific set of methods and approaches that ensure an optimal balance between effectiveness and feasibility of implementation (Fig. 2).

- Expert systems and rule-based algorithms. At the initial and basic maturity levels, the main applicable methods are expert systems and rule-based algorithms built on accumulated experience and maintenance standards:
 - Use of strictly defined rules and regulations reflecting scheduled timelines and procedures for M&R;

- Application of expert knowledge bases formed from the experience of the company's engineers and technical specialists;
- Rule-based decision support ("if-then" logic), where recommendations are generated based on predefined scenarios and rules.

Fig. 2. Methods of intelligent decision support in the M&R system.

These methods provide a basic level of intelligent M&R management, minimize human error, and improve process controllability when digital data availability is limited.

- Statistical analysis and diagnostic analytics methods. For enterprises at the basic and advanced maturity levels, it becomes possible to integrate statistical analysis and diagnostic methods:
 - Use of historical equipment runtime and failure data to build regression models and calculate failure probabilities;
 - Performing correlation analysis of equipment parameters and identifying causal relationships between operating conditions and failures;
 - Implementation of diagnostic algorithms based on analysis of equipment condition parameters (temperature, vibration, pressure, etc.).

These methods enable a higher level of analytical support by shifting from normative to actual condition-based maintenance.

- Predictive analytics and machine learning. At the advanced and optimized maturity levels, predictive analytics and machine learning methods become relevant:
 - Development of forecasting models based on large datasets about equipment technical condition;
 - Use of machine learning algorithms to automatically identify complex hidden dependencies and patterns that precede failures;
 - Implementation of digital twins and simulation models to predict M&R system behavior under various scenarios.

These methods not only respond to actual deviations but also predict potential risks, enabling proactive actions and optimized maintenance schedules.

- Integrated intelligent decision support systems. The highest form of intelligent implementation is the creation of integrated systems that combine all the above approaches:
 - o Automated data collection and processing from production assets;
 - o Dynamic adaptation of M&R plans based on changing operating conditions and equipment status;
 - o Real-time interactive support for operators in selecting optimal decisions.

Such systems ensure maximum M&R management efficiency, minimize unplanned downtime, and enable a shift to condition-based maintenance models.

In solving the tasks of using IDSS in managing M&R activities for the studied enterprise, the following action plan is proposed (Table 2):

Table 2. Steps for implementing a strategy of intelligent decision support in the M&R system.

Steps	Action
Development of decision support algorithms	Identify task types: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Failure prediction (predictive analytics). - Fault diagnostics based on historical data. - Optimization of maintenance schedules considering failure probabilities. - Automatic prioritization of maintenance requests. Choose analysis methods: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expert rules (logic-based reasoning from formalized knowledge). - Machine learning (classification and regression methods). - Statistical models (trend and anomaly analysis). Develop software modules for automatic data analysis and recommendation transfer into the M&R management system (CMMS, ERP).
Use of expert systems to automate fault diagnostics	Develop inference rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Analyze typical failures and related parameters. - Determine likely causes of faults using the knowledge base. - Formalize decision-making logic for automatic diagnostics. Create a base of expert solutions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Describe standard solutions for common failures. - Include recommendations for preventive measures. Develop an interface for interaction with technical specialists: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enable expert verification of recommendations before implementation. - Feedback mechanisms to improve the system based on real data.

Gradual introduction of machine learning, starting with analysis of accumulated data and predictive model creation

Select tasks for ML:

- Failure prediction based on sensor time series data.
- Fault type classification.
- Maintenance schedule optimization.

Data preparation:

- Cleaning, normalization, and formatting of data for ML compatibility.
- Feature selection impacting failure probability.

Develop and test models:

- Regression models for predicting Remaining Useful Life (RUL).
- Neural network algorithms for anomaly detection.
- Incident clustering for automatic fault classification.

Deploy models into the M&R system:

- Automatic generation of maintenance recommendations.
- Integration of models with equipment monitoring systems (SCADA, IoT).

Integrate the knowledge base with existing M&R management systems (CMMS, ERP, SCADA)

Integration with enterprise systems:

- CMMS (Computerized Maintenance Management System) - manages M&R data (work orders, failures, repairs). Integration allows automatic updates to the knowledge base and use of historical data for failure prediction.
- ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning) - manages financial and material resources for M&R.
- SCADA (Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition) - real-time equipment monitoring and control system.

Key integration steps:

- Configure data flows between M&R systems and analytical modules.
- Automate transfer of failure predictions into the M&R dispatch system.
- Create a unified interface for working with analytical data within the M&R system.

Define Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to evaluate the success of intelligent methods implementation

Main KPIs:

- MTBF (Mean Time Between Failures) - equipment reliability indicator.
- MTTR (Mean Time to Repair) - time required to fix a fault.
- Percentage of predicted failures - share of incidents forecasted before actual occurrence.
- Reduction of unplanned downtime - decrease in equipment non-operational time.
- Maintenance cost optimization - evaluation of cost reduction through intelligent planning.

The proposed sequence of steps toward intelligent decision support in the M&R system is not merely a logically constructed chain of actions but a justified and necessary

implementation strategy that ensures maximum efficiency and controllability of the digital transformation process.

Each step in this strategy has its own rationale and functional significance, forming a coherent and manageable process of transitioning to the intelligentization of the M&R system:

- Development of decision support algorithms is the starting point, as without clearly defined tasks and formalized algorithms, it is impossible to create a functional intelligent system. At this stage, models for data processing and recommendation generation are built, which will later enable automation of key M&R management functions.
- Implementation of expert systems for automating fault diagnostics acts as a bridge between the enterprise's accumulated practical experience and digital management methods. This step allows for the use of expert knowledge in a structured format, ensures standardization of diagnostic approaches, and lays the foundation for further development of analytical models.
- Gradual implementation of machine learning methods is a critical phase enabling the shift from scheduled and reactive maintenance to a predictive management model. Such a transition cannot happen instantly; the phased approach allows the necessary data to accumulate, the models to be tested in practice, and implementation risks to be reduced.
- Integration of the knowledge base and analytical models with existing enterprise management systems (CMMS, ERP, SCADA) ensures a complete digital framework and transforms intelligent support from an auxiliary tool into a core component of both operational and strategic M&R management.
- Defining key performance indicators (KPIs) completes the chain and turns the IDSS implementation process into a manageable and measurable project. Only through a system of indicators can achieved results be objectively assessed, the economic effect recorded, and continuous improvement of the intelligent system ensured.

Thus, each step in this strategy is not an isolated action but an interconnected element ensuring progressive development and sustainable implementation of intelligent decision support in the M&R system of an industrial enterprise.

RESULTS

This research identified and justified the key conditions necessary for the successful implementation of IDSS in the M&R system of an industrial enterprise. It revealed the main factors affecting the feasibility and effectiveness of applying intelligent solutions in M&R process management.

A methodology for the phased implementation of IDSS was developed, taking into account the maturity level of the enterprise's M&R system.

It was found that enterprises with a low maturity level, primarily characterized by reactive equipment maintenance, are not capable of effectively using advanced analytical algorithms

due to the lack of high-quality data and digital infrastructure. For such enterprises, priority tasks include process standardization, creation of a knowledge base on equipment condition and common failures.

Conversely, enterprises with a higher maturity level are ready to adopt predictive analytics, machine learning methods, and expert systems that enable intelligent M&R process management.

The practical implementation of the proposed approach allowed for the following outcomes:

- Formulation and justification of the stages for creating conditions for IDSS implementation;
- Identification of potential risks associated with the digital transformation of the M&R system;
- Development of specific steps for executing the strategy of intelligent decision support.

The results confirm that successful IDSS implementation is only possible through a systematic approach and strict adherence to a logical sequence of actions. Each stage—from maturity level assessment to algorithm development, integration with enterprise digital systems, and performance evaluation—is interconnected and essential.

The proposed comprehensive approach enables the creation of a fully functional intelligent preventive maintenance system that can improve process reliability, reduce costs, and increase the efficiency of maintenance management at the enterprise.

DISCUSSION

The approach presented demonstrates that the success of implementing intelligent methods directly depends on the initial conditions of the enterprise, particularly the maturity level of the M&R system and the degree of process digitalization. This supports the notion that advanced intelligent solutions cannot be directly replicated across enterprises with a low level of organizational and informational maturity.

A strength of the proposed approach is its phased and adaptive nature, which helps minimize investment and organizational risks by gradually increasing functionality and transitioning from simple expert systems to predictive analytics and machine learning methods. This strategy ensures the resilience of transformation processes and allows enterprises to adapt to changing external conditions.

At the same time, the research has identified several limitations, including:

- The need for a prolonged data accumulation period (especially in low-digitization environments);
- Limited applicability of complex machine learning models without adequate information infrastructure;
- High personnel qualification requirements for working with intelligent systems and interpreting results.

Given these limitations, it can be concluded that future research should focus on the development of adaptive IDSS implementation models that consider industry specifics and initial enterprise maturity levels.

Special attention should be given to:

- Developing methodologies for accelerated knowledge base formation;
- Tools to ensure data quality;
- Mechanisms for evaluating the economic effectiveness of intelligent system deployment at different maturity levels and in various industrial sectors.

CONCLUSION

This study confirmed the necessity of a systematic and phased approach to implementing IDSS in the M&R system of an industrial enterprise.

One of the key conclusions is that the effectiveness of intelligent methods depends directly on the maturity level of the M&R system and the degree of digitalization of the production environment.

Enterprises at the initial development stages must first:

- Standardize processes,
- Implement digital tools for data collection and accumulation,
- Develop a centralized knowledge base.

Without these steps, implementing advanced intelligent algorithms becomes inappropriate and ineffective.

For enterprises with a higher maturity level, opportunities arise to apply:

- Predictive analytics,
- Machine learning methods,
- Expert systems.

This ensures a shift to a more efficient equipment maintenance model—from scheduled maintenance to condition- and prediction-based service.

The developed methodology and proposed sequence of steps:

- Reduce risks in IDSS implementation,
- Improve the manageability of M&R system transformation,
- Achieve a sustainable economic effect.

Therefore, successful implementation of intelligent decision support in M&R requires not only new technologies but also thorough preparation, including:

- Assessing the current state,
- Building digital data flows,
- Integrating with enterprise management systems,
- Creating a performance evaluation system.

The results of this research can be used in practical industrial activities to build digital transformation strategies for M&R systems and may also serve as a basis for further scientific research in the field of intelligent decision support systems in industrial management.

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